

HARMS ASPECTS OF FAST FOOD FOR HUMAN LIFE

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Annotation: *This article discusses the harmful effects of fast food on human life. At the same time, it was also discussed about the diseases caused through fast food in the human body.*

Key words: *fast food, lifestyle, unhealthy eating, follow a diet, junk food.*

Introduction

Fast food is a type of [mass-produced](#) food designed for commercial resale, with a strong priority placed on speed of service. It is a commercial term, limited to food sold in a [restaurant](#) or store with frozen, preheated or precooked ingredients and served in packaging for [take-out](#)/takeaway. Fast food was created as a commercial strategy to accommodate large numbers of busy commuters, travelers and [wage workers](#). In 2018, the fast food industry was worth an estimated \$570 billion globally. [Fast food restaurants](#) are traditionally distinguished by the [drive-through](#). Outlets may be stands or [kiosks](#), which may provide no shelter or seating, or fast food restaurants (also known as quick service restaurants). [Franchise](#) operations that are part of [restaurant chains](#) have standardized foodstuffs shipped to each restaurant from central locations. Many fast foods tend to be high in [saturated fat](#), sugar, salt and calories. Fast food consumption has been linked to increased risk of [cardiovascular disease](#), [colorectal cancer](#), [obesity](#), [high cholesterol](#), [insulin resistance conditions](#) and [depression](#). These correlations remain strong even when controlling for confounding lifestyle variables, suggesting a strong association between fast food consumption and increased risk of disease and early mortality. Fast food outlets are take-away or take-out providers that promise quick service. Such fast food outlets often come with a "drive-through" service

that lets customers order and pick up food from their vehicles. Others have indoor or outdoor seating areas where customers can eat on-site. The boom in IT services has allowed customers to order food from their homes through their smartphone apps in recent times. Nearly from its inception, fast food has been designed to be eaten "on the go," often does not require traditional [cutlery](#), and is eaten as a [finger food](#). Common menu items at fast food outlets include [fish and chips](#), [sandwiches](#), [pitas](#), [hamburgers](#), [fried chicken](#), [french fries](#), [onion rings](#), [chicken nuggets](#), [tacos](#), [pizza](#), [hot dogs](#), and [ice cream](#), though many fast food restaurants offer "slower" foods like [chili](#), [mashed potatoes](#), and [salads](#). At the same time, in the article, we will study some other harms of fast food.

Main body

Why fast food is harmful to the body, is high in saturated animal fat. In order to save money, fast food establishments use margarines, which are cheap fat substitutes containing transgenic fats obtained from liquid fat thanks to special processing it turns out to be solid fat. The harm of this fat is that it increases the cholesterol level in the blood, puts a greater strain on liver, disrupts metabolism, adversely affects cardiovascular system. Frequent consumption of fast food causes a person to develop depression.

The fatty acids in these foods are absorbed into the part of the brain that responds to emotions. As a result, this person causes symptoms of depression. Also, it is correct to make a person who likes fast food fat. Regular consumption of fast food, excessive consumption of fatty foods, and excessive consumption of sweets lead to diseases of the intestinal system. Fast food contains trans fats, unsaturated fatty acids. It increases the amount of harmful cholesterol in the body. Trans fat is known to be a double whammy for heart disease: eating trans fat increases the level of bad cholesterol - LDL (low-density lipoprotein).

Instead of this expression, it and stroke it to run if. It can be put on the wall of the blood, which prevents the finding of blood. It can also cause cancer. And the gaseous part comes from the production of disease-intestinal system. We are well aware of the bad nutrition purchase agreement that many have received. For example, diseases of the liver, gall bladder, gastrointestinal tract, blood vessels, endocrine system are often explained as complications of unhealthy eating.

But the same factor can cause brain diseases, especially mental retardation. Australian scientists came to this conclusion at the end of their research.

In particular, the death of brain tissue is observed in dementia. This happens due to the lack of acetylcholine. As a result, 60% of such patients develop Alzheimer's disease, and the disease worsens over time.

Australian experts believe that completely avoiding harmful foods will significantly reduce the risk of such cases. Because saturated fats and trans fats in some foods accelerate the development of dementia. These include fatty dairy products, including butter, as well as chocolate, meat, palm and coconut oils.

Trans fats are especially common in today's parlance of fast food, fried foods and snacks, and store-bought baked goods, particularly cakes and cookies.

According to research, people who eat the above foods have a much higher risk of mental retardation and brain diseases. People who follow a diet, that is, refrain from consuming unsaturated fats, have a lower risk of developing cognitive disorders.

If you think McDonald's makes money selling cheeseburgers, fries, and milkshakes, you're wrong. In fact, this company is the largest owner of retail property on the planet. It opens franchised local restaurants around the world (licensed to operate under the McDonald's trademark, in accordance with production standards) and earns a large income from rent collection. And you can save ingredients so that food is cheap: only in this case people often look at a restaurant near the house.

The next time you're craving a hamburger and a soda, remember that fast food and its consequences are scary, even if you don't eat it every day, but once a month. That's why I include fast food in the list of the best foods to avoid and advise everyone to avoid this "junk food". For more information about the fast food industry, see the book "Fast Food Nation"... You can read about how the modern food industry shapes our addiction and addiction to food. Fast food has quickly gained popularity among different age groups. Some people do not suspect the dangers of fast food. Parents buy their children hamburgers and fries, and then they face a number of health problems in their children, including obesity.

Fast food or "fast food" - fast food that can be consumed quickly and conveniently by the customer. Excess sugar can lead to obesity and diabetes, disruption of the endocrine system and metabolism. A large amount of salt is very harmful for the heart and kidneys. Our body needs very little salt, excess salt is harmful to the body.

Fast food is very high in calories due to its high fat and sugar content. A large number of empty calories leads to obesity and digestive system problems. Fatty fast foods have a negative effect on the liver and pancreas. Fast food can be as addictive as alcohol or nicotine. To make fast food very tasty, various food additives are used in its preparation. Chemical elements accumulate in body cells and can cause cancer. Some people's immunity is weakened and allergies can develop. Food additives have a negative effect on all internal organs. Preservatives can even affect a person's appearance in the form of skin problems.

Trans fats have a negative effect on blood vessels and cause atherosclerosis, as well as the development of cancer and cardiovascular diseases. Children who grow up eating fast food are more likely to misbehave in school and get poor grades. For the younger generation, fast food is dangerous, because the body is still developing, and how it will be depends on the composition of the plate. An unbalanced menu leads to obesity, disorders in the endocrine and immune systems, which in turn affects physical and mental development in the future. Pizza, shawarma, french fries, grilled chicken, hot dog, chips, hamburger, hamburger.

It is better to replace fast food with fruits or vegetables rich in fiber and vitamins. One apple serves as an excellent snack that compensates for the lack of vitamins C and E, which are the best antioxidants.

There is nothing healthier than home-cooked food, try to avoid fatty foods and high-calorie foods and follow the principles of a balanced diet, and this is the only way to maintain your health and figure. At the same time, the incidence of obesity among children and adolescents in the developed countries of the world is constantly increasing: 25% of adolescents are overweight, and 15% are obese. Being overweight in childhood is a major factor in obesity in adulthood: 50 percent of children who are overweight at age 6 will become obese as adults, and this probability increases to 80 percent during adolescence. In developing China with a population of over 1.4 billion, the prevalence of childhood overweight and obesity has increased rapidly. In 2016, the proportion of Chinese children with obesity was 17.2% of boys and 9.11% of girls. Therefore, combating the epidemic of childhood obesity is of great importance in almost all countries of the world. Among adolescents aged 12-18 years, the percentage of energy consumption from home-made products is decreasing, while the percentage of energy consumption from fast food and fast food is constantly increasing. Around the world, fast food is promoted in different ways. Various ways to encourage the purchase of fast food products are involved: from sponsoring sports or cultural competitions with attractive prizes, from advertising on television with animation and cartoons, to attracting famous athletes and actors to advertise these products. In addition to television advertising, other mass media (radio, magazines), propaganda posters, and billboards are used.

Movie theaters and other public places are actively involved in fast food marketing. All of these aggressive manipulations play an important role in promoting unhealthy diets high in fat, sodium or sugar in children. In modern families living in big cities, fast food is gaining popularity because working parents have less time to prepare food. Children spend a lot of time outside the home, participate in extracurricular activities after school, and eat fast food at school or elsewhere. Thus,

according to a prospective study of 9,919 adolescents who participated in the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health (USA), there was a positive correlation between increased fast food consumption and increased body mass index (BMI) in all adolescents. was determined. Socio-economic status is an important factor associated with increased consumption of fast food. At the same time, manufacturers take into account the peculiarities of national cuisine, which also attracts children and teenagers. This trend is typical for all segments of the population: for example, children from wealthy families prefer fast food to traditional food, despite their parents' financial resources and good knowledge in the field of nutrition. Psychological attachment to fast food restaurants is demonstrated even in overweight children who recognize fast food logos significantly more than other products. Factors associated with preference for fast food include convenience, convenience, taste, price, and fast service at a fast food outlet. Many people who love fast food choose this type of food, despite knowing the negative consequences of eating unhealthy food. The link between fast food and obesity in children and adolescents A number of studies have identified a link between fast food and childhood obesity. A study was conducted between 2004 and 2009 among 2,136 7th grade students (aged 12-13) in Japan. The results showed that the waist-to-height ratio in adolescents is related to fast food. Given that fast food is designed to be absorbed very quickly, many studies have recently been conducted to investigate the effect of the speed of food consumption on metabolic properties. Children who eat more quickly have increased energy intake (larger appetite), increased BMI, and abdominal obesity. Many population studies confirm that faster food absorption is associated with increased energy intake during meals, higher BMI, and obesity. A two-fold difference in caloric intake was found between active and sedentary children: fast eaters consumed an average of 75% more calories than slow eaters.

Hamburgers, like other fast food, contain a large amount of salt (the human norm is 1/3 teaspoon per day). Two hamburgers contain the daily value of salt. Also broken They also try to hide products with salt or spices. From whom Exceeding the daily salt norm primarily affects the kidneys. Salt the body retains water, which causes swelling and can increase arterial pressure. The reason for the negative effects of fast food on human health the way they are used. "Fast food" is taken quickly, on the go, to accommodate a short lunch break. That's why it is very difficult for the stomach to cope with large pieces that are poorly chewed food filled with carbonated drinks, and not gastric juice spices, mayonnaise, can cope with a large variety of ingredients sauces, ketchup, their main role is to hide the true taste and smell damaged products.

Behavioral and nutritional strategies play an important role in preventing childhood obesity. In contrast to the concept of fast food (fast food), some researchers

are actively implementing the "slow food" model as the most important concept of behavioral nutrition. This model is officially recommended for weight management because it has been shown to control satiety. Such simple lifestyle changes that can affect a person's risk of obesity are important for cost-effectiveness prevention strategies. School programs and health education can also implement behavioral policies to improve children's eating habits. Bargaining is one of the most effective strategies for buying healthy foods. Lowering the price of low-fat snacks and placing special low-fat labels will lead to a significant increase in their consumption by teenagers. At the same time, in some countries of the world, for example, in Great Britain, they have already begun to add sections on healthy eating to textbooks for schoolchildren, which is certainly a positive step in the fight against the consequences of fast food, also encourages children and their parents to eat a balanced healthy diet. Therefore, she is a prime example of the harm that fast food causes. Today we can safely say that fast food is only harmful to health, and

its benefit is minimal. No fast food can replace healthy food, and he is not worth putting his own health on the line.

CONCLUSION

Given the clear link between children and adolescents' fast food consumption, families and schools should strongly discourage the consumption of unhealthy foods that lead to weight gain and obesity-related diseases. should control. Stop selling junk food to kids with cute signs and gifts. This can be one way to improve children's nutrition. It can cause various health problems not only in children, but also in adults. Among the strategies aimed at promoting healthy eating, one of the most important is the availability of healthy food at lower prices and in more attractive presentations.

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